

Some Mixed Metal Complexes of Propylenediamine-bis(isatin)

ALY M. A. HASSAAN^a, AHMED K. ABU AL-NASR^b and M. A. KHALIFA^c

^aChemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Minia University, El-Minia, Egypt

^bChemistry Department, Faculty of Teachers, Al-Madinah Al-Munawarah, P. O. Box 1343, Saudi Arabia

^cChemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Alexandria University, Alexandria, Egypt

Manuscript received 12 April 1996, accepted 14 May 1996

There is growing interest in studies on multimetallic complexes¹. They have active sites in a variety of metalloenzymes and play a significant role in industrial catalysis. In the present work, we report the synthesis of some mixed metal complexes of propylenediamine-bis(isatin).

Results and Discussion

The reaction mechanism for the formation of the complexes is given in Scheme 1. In the preparation of heterobinuclear complexes, a low temperature and short reaction time are necessary otherwise the dissociation reaction, $2[\text{CuLM}]^{2+} \rightleftharpoons [\text{Cu}_2\text{L}]^{2+} + [\text{M}_2\text{L}]^{2+}$ will take place. The analytical data (Table 1) suggest that the reaction of CuL with $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and $\text{UO}_2(\text{OAc})_2$ produces binuclear complexes $\text{CuLCu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1) and $\text{CuLUO}_2(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2) respectively. The reaction of CuL with $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ produces trinuclear complexes of the type $(\text{CuL})_2\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (3) and $(\text{CuL})_2\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (4) respectively. The $[\text{CuLCu}(\text{OAc})^+(\text{OH})^- \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complex

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd. no	Compd.	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)			Λ $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		C	H	N	
1	$\text{CuLCu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	23.34	2.82	8.49	89.64
		(32.94)	(2.60)	(8.09)	
2	$\text{CuLUO}_2(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	32.68	3.59	6.38	5.86
		(32.33)	(3.28)	(6.56)	
3	$(\text{CuL})_2\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	39.53	2.74	13.65	8.27
		(39.10)	(2.91)	(13.20)	
4	$(\text{CuL})_2\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	39.39	2.68	13.42	12.48
		(39.07)	(2.91)	(13.19)	
5	$[\text{CuLCu}(\text{OAc})](\text{OH}) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	44.75	3.58	9.78	93.89
		(44.28)	(3.86)	(9.84)	

(5) was obtained on refluxing $\text{CuLCu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in ethanol in the presence of NaOAc (Scheme 1). The molar conductivity values in DMF at 25° indicate a non-electrolytic nature of the complexes obtained except for complexes 1 and 5. On comparison of ir spectra of CuL with those of

Scheme 1

*Present Address : Chemistry Department, Faculty of Teachers, Al-Madinah Al-Munawarah, P. O. Box 1343, Saudi Arabia.

mixed metal complexes, a higher energy shift of the bands at 1 300 and 1 610 cm^{-1} of CO- and the conjugated CN-stretching vibration respectively, were observed due to the increasing constraint introduced by the oxygen-bridging². In the spectra of complex 5, the bands at 1 555 and 1 408 cm^{-1} may be attributed to μ_{as} and μ_{s} of the acetate group. Furthermore, $\Delta\mu = 147 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicates its bidentate nature. In all the complexes, the bands due to water molecules are observed at 3 390–3 350 and 1 270–1 260 cm^{-1} attributable to OH stretching and bending vibrations respectively. Complex 1 displays very strong bands at 1 120 cm^{-1} characteristic of ionic ClO_4^- . In the spectra of complex 2, the band at 1 390 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the sym. COO^- stretching vibration. Furthermore, the bands at 985 and 880 cm^{-1} may be ascribed to the asymmetric and symmetric vibrational frequencies of UO_2^{II} moiety. With respect to complexes 3 and 4, the bands around 1 290 and 1 030 cm^{-1} may correspond to μ_1 and μ_2 vibrations of unidentate nitrate group³. The electronic spectra of complex 1 (in DMF) display a band at 18 600 cm^{-1} due to $d-d$ transition of Cu^{II} in square-planar N_2O_2 sites, whereas 5 displays a band at 18 400 cm^{-1} which could be taken as evidence for the distortion from the planar configuration. The spectra of 2 show bands at 22 727, 28 328 and 18 900 cm^{-1} . The first two bands may be due to the uranyl ion⁴, and the third band could be attributed to the CuN_2O_2 chromophore. The electronic spectra of 3 and 4 show a broad band at 22 800 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to $L \rightarrow M$ transition. The band is so strong that the $f-f$ bands are obscured. On the basis of the above discussion, the suggested structures for the investigated mixed metal complexes are given in Scheme 1.

Experimental

All reagents purchased from commercial sources were used as such. The complexed ligand (CuL) of propylenediamine-bis(isatin) with copper(II) was prepared according to our previous work⁵.

The mixed metal complexes were prepared as follows. To an ethanolic solution (50 ml) of the previously reported CuL complex (0.01 mol), the appropriate $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{UO}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.005 mol) dissolved in the minimum quantity of ethanol was added slowly. The reaction mixture was refluxed gently on a water-bath for 60 min and then cooled. The resulting complexes were washed with absolute ethanol, dried and preserved in a desiccator.

References

1. M. NAKAMURA, H. OKAWA and S. KIDA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1983, **62**, 201; S. L. LAMBERT, C. L. SPIRO, R. R. GAGNE and D. N. HENDRICKSON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, **21**, 68; M. NAKAMURA, M. MIKURIYA, H. OKAWA and S. KIDA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1981, **54**, 1825; C. J. CONNOR, D. P. FREBERG and E. SINN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, **18**, 1077; N. H. PILKINGTON and R. ROBSON, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1970, **23**, 2 225; S. L. LAMBERT and D. N. HENDRICKSON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1978, **18**, 2683; R. R. GAGNE, C. A. KOVAL and T. SMITH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **101**, 8367; U. CASSELLATO, P. A. VIGATO and M. VIDALI, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1977, **23**, 31.
2. E. SINN and S. M. HARRIS, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1969, **4**, 391.
3. K. UENO and A. E. MARTELLI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, **60**, 1270.
4. L. SACCONI, G. CAROTI and P. PAOLETTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 4247.
5. A. M. A. HASSAAN and M. A. KHALIFA, communicated.